

PRACTICAL APPROACH TO (FINANCIAL) RESOURCEFULNESS: A NECESSITY FOR SUSTAINABLE EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

Education is an expensive social service and requires adequate financial provision from all tiers of Government for a successful implementation of the educational programmes. However, the situations in Public Institutions signify continual inadequate fundings from the Government. The ongoing industrial action embarked upon by the Academic Staff Union of Universities in Nigeria is a typical effect of the inadequacy. Nevertheless, the educational institutions on their own can bring about some positive changes through financial resourcefulness. The study was designed to figure out the pragmatic approaches needed for sound management and strategic entrepreneurship, researching and leveraging that would lead the institutions into financial adequacy. The study intends to bring out the right orientation towards our academic researches and prescribe a reasonable approach that is adaptable to the Business Model Innovation defined by Henry Chesbrough and Richard S. Rosembloom from Harvard Business School. The effect of the model is that researches would be information-based, and oriented towards the addressing the nagging societal needs, producing things of value which may lead to financial resourcefulness.

INTRODUCTION

Education is an expensive social service and requires financial provision from all tiers of Government for a successful implementation of the educational programs. (National Policy on Education [NPE], 1977). Even though this statement is clearly written in the document of the Nigerian national Policy of Education, the poor funding of schools and institutions today is a clear evidence of its poor implementation. Dilapidated conditions of public schools, shortage of teachers, poorly-equipped libraries, bad roads and infrastructures, delays in the payment of teachers' salaries and allowances. The incessant industrial strikes embarked upon by the teachers' associations are direct reactions to their poor working conditions. If the Government of a nation cannot properly harness her resources to finance education then it is a big challenge to the owners of private institutions to ensure that they do not fall into such a mistake.

Parents want to see good teachers – highly trained teachers, Good Hostels, and facilities, and good infrastructure, beautiful environment conducive for learning. For a University not to lose her credibility these items must not just be provided but should be maintained and sustained. Since education is a dynamic process, her monetary affairs should not be hampered by any factor because any shortage or mismanagement of such would make the University to lose its essence and credibility.

Nigeria as a nation is slow in terms of development. We don't have good roads and infrastructure, poor in science and technology and we have very poor economic power. These factors militate against the smooth running of educational system in the country. Education is expensive, bad economy is additional burden!

Now, education is expensive and it has to be provided for. This calls for financial resourcefulness on the part of educational stakeholders. The work cannot be done by the stake holders alone, the teachers have to rise to the task. All avenues of providing money for education should be explored. Money is needed to train and retrain teachers, to buy materials and equipment, to furnish laboratories and workshops, to expand the scope of existing programmes, to create new programmes and generally to supply the day-to-day needs of an institution.

Nigeria's poor economy, coupled with marketing competitiveness among private institutions would not make the tuition fees to be enough as the only source of financing Higher Institutions. Therefore, the school managements need to combine both the intellectual and tangible resources of the institution to buoy

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the system out of debilitating poverty. Her pecuniary resources, her intellectual acumens, her corporate rights and privileges need to be channeled towards fruitfulness and growth.

By carefully studying the Nigerian economic system, looking for the challenges, the factors that pose as impediments to its growth, the abandoned or neglected actions/policies that would have made the country rich economically, the pitfalls to avoid, the areas that need fortification; we can easily establish a strong economic system that will be sustainable.

1.1 Facts That You Need To Know about the Nigerian Economy

- Nigerian Population - 169 millions.
- 70% of the population lives in poverty.
- Nearly 61 percent of the population or about 100 million people live on less than \$1 a day.
- About 35 millions youth are jobless.
- Second highest rated of maternal mortality in the world - WHO
- 90% of the Raw materials used are imported
- Nigeria is Oil-rich.
- Ravaged in Political turmoil and Corruption.
- About 120 million of the population don't have access to electricity

1.2 Financial Resourcefulness

What is Financial Resourcefulness?

- **Financial**:- Pecuniary resources (monetary affairs);
- **Resourcefulness**: - Fertility in expedients; Skill or ingenuity in meeting any situation.
- **Financial Resourcefulness** can be defined as making skillful use of our funds, revenue, income, intellect, power, strength and position in such a way that will bring multiplication of wealth and progress.

Why Financial Resourcefulness in Higher Institutions?

- High interest rates.
- High cost of materials/facilities.
- Expansion.
- Meeting Competitive challenge among other Universities.
- Reformation and Transformation.
- Preparation for sophisticated investments.
- Privatization and Concessioning.
- Financial back-up in form of Reserve.

What Financial resourcefulness is NOT!

- Not by receiving Foreign aids.
- Not donation(s) from philanthropist(s).
- Not submission of papers to international or local journals.
- Not tuition fees – other institutions have tuition fees as well.
- Not by spending many hours in the laboratory.
- Not personal achievements or compliments.

1.3 Philosophy of Nigerian Education

Financial resourcefulness is attainable if we can go back to the landmark which the Nigerian pioneers of educational system had made. This landmark is evident in the five main national objectives as they are itemized in the philosophy of Nigerian Education. Nigerian Education is to be for the building of;

- 1) a free and democratic society;
- 2) a just and egalitarian society;
- 3) a united, strong and self-reliant nation;

- 4) a great and dynamic economy;
- 5) a land of bright and full opportunities for all citizens.

(NPE, 1977)

The last three (3) objectives are the factors that bring financial resourcefulness because they indirectly bring about job creation and wealth generation. When these objectives are achieved we will have a country with stable and dynamic economy. Wealth generation does not come directly but it comes when we meet the societal needs.

‘Wealth, like happiness is never attained when sought after directly. It always comes as a by-product of providing a useful service’ – Henry Ford.

University education is meant for national development through researching in the areas that the society need. This is clearly written in the NPE (1977) section 5 No. 35: “If university research is to assist national development, it should be relevant to the nation’s development goals. To ensure this relevance:

- (a) Government will direct the National Universities Commission, the National Educational Research Council, and other appropriate bodies to identify the areas of need and priority. Universities can base their research programs on these.
- (b) Government will support closer links between the universities, industry and the various Research Councils.
- (c) Government will encourage locally-based industries to develop direct links with research institutes and universities to facilitate research into their products and problems.
- (d) Universities will be required to keep both government and industry better informed about their research results.
- (e) Government will ensure effective utilization of the results of universities’ research and promising research results which at first look unprofitable but are likely to pay off in the long run will be taken up and developed by government.

University education is meant to practically tackle the societal needs by recommending research-based solutions to the government for execution. What this will normally lead to are;

- Rise in the number of the university patents.
- Creation of spin-out factories.
- Recognition of the university as a high-ranking institution.
- Financial enrichment.
- Increased level of cooperation and collaboration with other companies/universities of related achievements in form of MOU.

The financial resourcefulness of a university depends much on how seriously the management of the institution is ready to apply the intellectuality and the technicality of the institution to solve the societal/community needs. If our researches are not relevant to the community need, we should bury such because the community would neither recognize it nor buy it.

1.4 Research, Innovation and University System

For a university to be financially resourceful, it is not enough for researchers to approach research in the old manners of going to the laboratory to perform experiment with the mind that sometimes in the future useful products might come out of them. This linear or supply-push approach to innovation is well past its sell-by date. The scientific researches truly bring to light certain facts that are explained in empirical forms but they do not lead to a wholesome innovation. This may probably be because the long-hour stays in the laboratory is out of mere curiosity – curiosity of finding new things. If we are to continue with this approach and expect all industrial ideas to come directly from universities, we would not even have the tin-opener.

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The linear model approach to innovation had been used by the past scientists – laws of motion was discovered by Isaac Newton but there is a complex interchange between laws of motion and creation of automobiles. There is a complex interchange between Faraday's laws of electricity and the creation of electric generator. Likewise there is a complex interchange between Maxwell's equations of electromagnetism and the discovery of radio. In fact most of the discoveries were made by enthusiastic amateurs like D.E. Hughes and Thomas Edison who are just interested in finding solutions to human needs. In Nigerian universities, we have many researchers boasting of having written many papers but we have very few innovators. We have to take note of this; Researches gulp money, innovations refund money; researching on its own do not create jobs, innovation does; research do not generate wealth, innovation does; research do not raise the Gross Domestic product of a nation, innovation does. In fact, it is through innovation that we can put our raw materials into effective usage for manufacturing.

Nigerian educational system had over-stayed on the linear approach to innovation to the extent that the nation is being overwhelmed by bursting challenges such as lack of employment, poverty, slowness of economic development, lack of indigenous technology, and so on. Nigeria has to be delivered out of the shackles of poverty and the universities have important roles to play. We should know that the funding agencies of various researches would expect result in form of wealth creation. By following this linear approach to innovation we would not be able to meet up with this challenge or if at all, it would be on timescales longer than that of the relevant product. Most of the funding agencies are from the developed nations – USA, UK and ASIA. These countries also adopt linear model to innovation which definitely will not yield any immediate result but their consolation is that at least they have vast numbers of innovations that they sell within and also exported to other countries and so they have robust economies, and science and innovation to them is yielding dividends.

Every country has its own peculiarities. Nigerian researchers should not continue with their long-hour stays on Lab benches trying to find out problem that yet, not exist or remote when there are nagging or debilitating issues at hand. They should train their faculties to be innovative as well. Their analytic approach to education should be synchronized with creative intelligence. That is the essence of university education and that is the only way financial resourcefulness can be achieved.

This does not mean that we are relegating the conventional model of researching. Of course, a university campus is a great place to garner new ideas, if you have run out of them yourself. Certainly, when you have built something bigger, more powerful than you have ever done before and it does not work, it is a great place to find the scholarship that will tell you where you went wrong. But this is all part of the university's vital role in thriving modern industrial economy. However industrial ideas (innovations) should come from our universities too. What we need is an understanding of the real value of both the seasoning of academic scientific creativity in industrial innovation and the ability to call on a university's specialist expertise with ease. This requires that the universities adopt funding strategies of meeting the needs of the society in a new, changed or different ways. This method is far more effective than the one many of us have at present; it is referred to by business schools as the 21st century innovation game.

Universities should channel investments not to where immediate highest short-term profit could be maximized, but where investment is needed for long-term robust and sustainable job-driven growth could be expected. Not seeking short-term highest return on investment, but long-term university monitored economic approach.

1.4.1 Why Must We Not Settle for a Low Key Investment?

Nigeria is a developing country and although her economic growth rate had been slow, the developed world had recently discovered that it is a promising land. Countries like US and China are interested in the country, more importantly after the economic crash of 2008. They have seen Nigeria as one of the emerging markets where they can invest at low interest rate and harvest bountifully at high margins. These countries are wealthier and more advanced in technology and so, they can produce in large quantities. Why should they take the glory of production alone?

1.4.2 Why are the advanced countries interested in Nigeria?

- Nigeria is blessed with mineral resources.
- We are not technologically advanced.
- We have comparatively very large population (cheap labour is available) (about 169 million).
- Most of our resources are been exported for manufacturing.
- Nigeria market is an emerging market not yet subject to the rules of the advanced markets; hence they see it as centre for competitiveness.
- Nigeria is at the verge of transition from developing country to a civilized country. In fact they knew that our slowness of advancement is as a result of poor leadership and not because we did not have the potentials.

Globalization would bring advancement to the country in the next 15 years, technology will be transferred in the country (majorly for profit making) and the indigenous companies and institutions need to measure up to the standard.

The Universities need to take businesses beyond the border of ‘Let us survive’ to the level of the national development. The country is full of business opportunities, it only requires discernments of sound entrepreneurs to identify the areas of needs and recommend to the University for researching and leveraging. The University has the advantage of deploying intellectuals of various expertises to examine critically the proposed areas, authenticate the values of the areas proposed, identifies the customers, devised the cost of production and develop strong capacity for take-off. This method is referred to as Business Model Innovation and it has been recommended as 21st Century innovation game.

1.5 Business Model Innovation

Business model innovation is the creation, reinvention or enhancement of a business model (describes the logic and principles that a firm uses to generate revenue) so that it satisfies customer needs (values proposition) in a new, changed or different way.

Henry Chesbrough and Richard S. Rosenbloom from Harvard Business School put forward an excellent definition for a business model innovation.

“The functions of a business model are to;

- Articulate the value proposition, that is, the value created for users by the offering based on the technology;
- Identify a market segment, that is, the users to whom the technology is useful and for what purpose;
- Define the structure of the value chain within the firm required to create and distribute the offering;
- Estimate the cost structure and profit potential of producing the offering, given the value proposition and value chain structure chosen;
- Describe the position of the firm within the value network linking suppliers and customers mentors and competitors;
- Formulate the competitive strategy by which the innovating firm will gain and hold advantage over rivals.

This approach is a nimble approach to innovation and it can be adapted to any business anywhere in the world.

The flow chart for the Business Model Innovation as designed by Alex Osterwalder is shown below.

Flow Chart For Business Model Innovation

Designed by Alex Osterwalder

Fig. 1. Business Model Innovation

The Business Model Innovation attaches much importance to the **value** that the company wants to create. The value is to be determined by joint efforts of **interdisciplinary partners** forming a network. This partner network must comprise of highly informed economists, sound entrepreneurs, scientific researchers and legal advisers. They are to develop the value proposals as they would be presented to the **targeted customer** (presentation is better done by the marketers). The objective of the marketer is to make the **potential customer** know the value in terms of comparative advantage derivable from patronizing the company.

The partner network form the major man-power resources of the company, they are to formulate the facilities and the materials needed for creating the product that would measure up to the standard of value planned. The entire cost of procuring facilities/equipments, of providing network of interdisciplinary experts so as to get the product of equivalent value is the **cost structure**.

The mutual understanding between the company and the customer will bring about patronization that is backed up with legal agreement. This relationship is to bring **Revenue Streams** to the company.

The Cost Structure and the Revenue Streams makes it easy for the company to do self-evaluation.

$$\text{Revenue} - \text{Cost of Production} = \text{Profit/Loss}$$

If it is positive it is success.

If it is negative it is failure.

However, profit or loss should not be based on the returns from the single transaction as the facilities continually would produce virtually an unending result!

1.5.1 Practical Application/Adaptability of Business Model Innovation to Business Demand

The CEO of Fan Milk Plc lamented that Nigeria, after 50 years of independence could not supply his company with Cow Milk to the extent that the company has to continually spend money to import this material from Brazil. He further said that it takes 300,000 diary cows to produce the milk that his company requires continually and regularly. He then wondered why Nigeria is enriching other countries and left herself fallowed. In conclusion, he said and I quote, “What Nigeria needs to do is to leverage on the areas where she has competitive advantages and stop unnecessary imitation of foreign countries”.

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To a University that wants to be financially resourceful, the statement from the CEO above is a mine of information and the required innovation of providing raw cow milk is adaptable to the Business Model above.

Partner Network: Students in the faculty of Agriculture particularly the Animal Science Students, Researchers from this field, Expert on the field, Economists' crew, Entrepreneurs, Legal Practitioners and as many others as the service may require.

Core Capacities: Calves for nurturing and experimentation, Facilities (Physical) for researching and experimentation, Landed Properties, Dairy Cows, Human Resources

Value Configuration: Production of raw milk from within the country, Relief from Importation of raw milk at high expense rate, Accessibility of raw milk by the company.

Cost structure: To be determined by the partner network in a progressive manner

Customer relationship: To be designed by the marketers (Business Administrators) and Legal Personnel.

Targeted Customers: Fan Milk PLC, Ibadan. Oyo, Nigeria, Eleyele Industrial Layout, P. O. Box 1617

Distribution Channels: To be determined by the Partner network e.g. by Self-delivery

Success/Failure: Self-evaluation

Value Proposition: Proposals to be made by the marketing body of the Partner network.

Revenue Streams: From the customer to the producer.

When a University embarks on a project like this successfully, she has succeeded in solving one of the problems in the country and therefore contributed to national development. As a consequence, the University would be financially enriched. This is just an example out of many. There are hundreds of raw materials that are being imported from foreign countries when in actual fact; they can be made available within. Prof. Peter Onwualu, the Director-General of the Raw Materials Research and Development Council (RMRDC) has confirmed that 90% of the raw materials used in the country were imported by manufacturers. One of the ways of raising the GDP of the country is by reducing substantially the volume of imported raw materials.

Onwualu said the reduction in the importation of raw materials would lead to the creation of jobs as well as the generation of wealth within the economy. He said that it would also improve the standard of living in the country. According to him, when such raw materials are harnessed, new processing industries will come up and new products will come into the market to help the people to make more money (Manufacturers Association of Nigeria [MAN], 2012).

Summary

Educational system of which university education is of paramount importance is the subject of national development. University education is meant for changing the community for the better by providing continuously, adequate manpower resources through proper training and researching. However, if this will be successful, there should be adequate funding for sustainability and growth. Therefore, University system needs to adopt Business Model of Innovation so as to produce those things that are marketable and relevant to the national development. This model therefore, requires co-operations and collaborations among experts of various endeavour: academic, professional, skilled, semi-skilled and the unskilled for singularity purpose of raising the economic growth of the nation.

RECOMMENDATIONS

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- The Office of the Development and Strategy should document the Industries in the country with raw materials they import and where they are imported from so as to make presentation to the Partner Network.
- The University should establish Innovation and Entrepreneurship Group.
- There should be a policy that upholds continuity of projects even after the incumbent administration has left for sustainable development
- There should be incentives for scientific researchers that procure solutions to the nagging needs of our immediate environment/Community most especially in the area of economic development.

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